

Boehmeria japonica (Linnaeus f.) Miquel: a new record to the flora of Bangladesh

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Abstract

Boehmeria japonica is reported for the first time from Bangladesh. This species was found in Hazarikhil Wildlife Sanctuary, Chittagong, Bangladesh.

The family Urticaceae consists of 1300 species and 47 genera, widely distributed in wet tropical regions and extending into temperate regions (Flora of China, 2018). The Plant List includes 387 scientific plant names of species rank for the genus *Boehmeria*; of these 96 are accepted species names (The Plant List, 2013). *Boehmeria japonica* (IPNI, 2005) was not reported in the relevant literature (Ahmed et al., 2009; Pasha & Uddin, 2013; Rahman & Hassan, 2017), therefore, this species (Figure 1) is reported here for the first time from Bangladesh. Specimens (n=2) of species were collected from Kalapainna Chora, Hazarikhil Wildlife Sanctuary, Harualchari, Vuzpur, Fatikchari, Chittagong, Bangladesh. The photograph of species was taken during the field trip. The collected specimens were deposited at Bangladesh Forest Research Institute Herbarium (BFRIH). Those specimens were identified and described by consulting floristic literatures and databases (Ahmed et al., 2009; Airy-Shaw, 1966; Flora of China, 2018; Flowers of India, 2016; Pasha & Uddin, 2013; Prain, 1903; Rahman & Uddin, 1997; Rahman & Hassan, 2017; Roxburgh, 1814; The Plant List, 2013).

Our newly reported species can be characterized by a subshrubs or herbs perennial, simple or few branched. Leaves opposite, subequal in size; stipules lanceolate, petiolate; leaf blade dark green, suborbicular, orbicular-ovate, or ovate, papery, secondary veins 1-3 pairs along midvein, abaxial surface pubescent or sericeous along veins and veinlets, adaxial surface roughish, strigillose, base broadly cuneate, subrounded, or truncate, margin coarsely dentate, apex sometimes inconspicuously tricuspidate, lateral cusps shorter than terminal one. Dioecious; glomerules on axillary unbranched, or sometimes few-branched, spikelike branches; male spikes shorter than female spikes. Male flowers 4-merous,

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Figure 1. *Boehmeria japonica* collected from Hazarikhil Wildlife Sanctuary, Chittagong, Bangladesh

sessile; perianth lobes elliptic, strigose, connate at base. Fruiting perianth rhomboid-obovoid, compressed, smooth, strigose on shoulder, base stipitate or cuneate, apex with short neck, 2-toothed.

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